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Considerations of UV Light in Satellite based QKD Link Simulations

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Abstract

In this report we review the relevance of a satellite based quantum key distribution (SatQKD) network, analyse implications that different orbital geometries have on the yield of secret key length (SKL) and discuss the viability for using UV wavelengths in the context of SatQKD communications. A concise explanation of the theoretical background knowledge needed to understand the report is given, with an emphasis on quantum encryption, orbital mechanics and satellite based communications. Moreover, the current state of the field is summarized and its future development is explored.

Simulations of link losses due to diffraction of light between two satellites in low Earth orbit are conducted in conjunction with simulations of SKL generation rates for different orbital geometries. Our findings show that for two satellites orbiting at 530 km and 720 km above sea level (ASL), within a time window of $\Delta t = 351$ seconds (centered at the time of closest approach), a maximum SKL of $9.24 \cdot 10^8$ bits, $1.30 \cdot 10^9$ bits and a significantly higher SKL of $1.55 \cdot 10^{10}$ bits is achieved for anti-parallel, perpendicular and parallel orbits respectively.

Finally, relations between SKL generation rates, the relative orbital angle and system losses are explored.

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I. Introduction

In this section, the prime focus will be the motivational basis for the project, as well as a detailed explanation of the key concepts needed to understand the report and its implications.

This project is concerned with providing the reader with a better understanding for the implications that different satellite constellations and orbital parameters have on the generation of the secret key as well as the feasibility of SatQKD based communication networks using UV light.

While section 'A' will give motivation for the pursuit of this project, specific areas of interest such as advantages and disadvantages of quantum encryption over classical encryption methods, working principles of quantum encryption as well as key aspects of inter-satellite communications, will be covered in great detail in section 'B'.

A. Motivation

While classical encryption methods have been used to preserve secrecy and privacy for a very long time in that they are relatively safe, they are not without flaws [1]. Generally, we can distinguish between two types of cryptographic algorithms that are commonly used, that is, symmetric key cryptographic algorithms and (asymmetric) public key cryptographic algorithms [2].

The main difference between the two is that symmetric key algorithms use a single shared key to perform both encryption and decryption, whereas public key algorithms use two separate keys [3], one (public) for encryption and another one (private) for decryption.

While symmetric key algorithms are generally faster than public key algorithms, it is often difficult to find methods for distributing keys securely and efficiently [2]. Public key algorithms on the other hand don't rely on methods for 'key distribution', but rather on complex mathematical models [2, 3], resulting in slower but relatively secure encryption rates.

A major disadvantage of public key encryption, apart from being slower, is that it relies on a lack of computational power of a potential attacker, in order to be effective in rendering the communication lines safe [4]. For these reasons, symmetric key encryption methods are preferred for transferring large amounts of data.

Although classical encryption techniques can be easier to implement and have no effective range limitations, as advancements are made in quantum computing, quantum computers pose a bigger threat to the security of the classically encrypted communications with time [4]. For this reason in particular, it seems natural to shift the attention to a type of encryption method which is not reliant upon computational power, quantum encryption, that is, Quantum Key Distribution (QKD).

QKD is an important field of research as it has the potential of providing one of the most secure communications networks across the globe [5]. It is no different from classical encryption methods in that it uses the same general key sharing scheme, and just like classical encryption it requires authentication¹, however, it will be shown that due to the nature of Quantum Mechanics, QKD is a significant improvement over classical encryption when it comes to security.

QKD could potentially provide secure quantum encrypted communication links between satellites and ground. This technology thus has the potential of providing a secure global internet network

¹ Authentication is the process by which the modification of data is detected.

[1], which could enable distributed quantum sensors, clock synchronization for secure high-precision time information, and faster data processing through distributed quantum computing [1, 2].

However, there are some disadvantages to SatQKD based communications, since much of the information sent between satellites is lost. This loss of information occurs for various reasons, including the very nature of the protocol used to encrypt the information to be shared [4]. It is therefore worth looking into ways of minimizing loss of information where possible.

The intent of this project is to help expand our understanding and knowledge of QKD for inter-satellite communications. In particular, the project aims at investigating how different orbital geometries influence the amount of information that can be shared through inter-satellite quantum channels for a single pass, as well as the viability for SatQKD communication links using the UV portion of the electromagnetic spectrum.

For SatQKD communications UV light is a highly attractive possibility for mainly two reasons: first and foremost, photons in this range of frequencies carry more energy than radio or infrared signals, resulting in higher intensity over long distances, meaning a higher photon detection probability (PDP). Moreover, UV light has a relatively small overlap with the emission spectrum of the Sun compared to infrared and visible light, as it can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Diagram showing the solar emission spectrum for different wavelengths of light [6].

Before delving into an analysis to tackle this query, it is important to gather all the required background knowledge first.

B. Background Knowledge

1. Quantum Encryption

Broadly speaking, all encryption methods follow a certain scheme which is concerned with providing a unique shared key to two parties that want to send encrypted messages to one another [1]; with this key, only they can access that information. This is an over-simplification in that it does not take into account losses when sending the message (which could be due to many reasons) and the possibility of a third party trying to alter or gather the information.

The most commonly used and first ever protocol for encrypting messages in QKD, is the Bennett-Brassard 1984 (BB84) protocol [7], and it is concerned with generating a shared key between the two parties [4, 8]. In order to understand how BB84 works, consider the scenario for which two parties, 'Alice' and 'Bob' want to send encrypted messages to one another. For this purpose they must first generate a shared key that they can then use to encrypt and decrypt the messages. A concise explanation of the basic and ideal operation of the protocol is given below:

1. *Preparation.* Alice will use a single photon source to send 1 photon at a time to Bob and for each photon, she will randomly choose a state² [7], that is either horizontal/vertical or diagonal/anti-diagonal using a $\lambda/2$ -polarization plate as shown in Fig. 2 below [4]. Where the possible basis states available are given by Eq. (1):

$$\mathcal{B}_+ = \{ |0\rangle_+, |1\rangle_+ \}, \quad \mathcal{B}_x = \{ |0\rangle_x, |1\rangle_x \} \quad (1)$$

2. *Measurement.* Likewise, Bob will also randomly choose either the \mathcal{B}_+ or the \mathcal{B}_x basis for which to measure the photon in [4]. Note that the probability for which Bob will make the measurement in the same basis that Alice chose, i.e. the correct basis, is 50% and if he chooses the wrong basis, he still has a 50% probability of measuring the correct state.

3. *Basis reconciliation & key generation.* After the measurement process, Alice and Bob will share (over a classical communications link) which basis they chose for each photon, and only keep the bits for which they used the same basis [4, 7]. This results in a string of bits that they both share, namely the 'secret key'.

The secret key length can be calculated using Eq. (2):

$$\ell = \left[s_{X,0} + s_{X,1} [1 - h(\phi_X)] - \lambda_{EC} - 6 \log_2 \left(\frac{21}{\epsilon_s} \right) - \log_2 \left(\frac{2}{\epsilon_c} \right) \right] \quad (2)$$

with the binary entropy function: $h(x) = -x \log_2(x) - (1-x) \log_2(1-x)$.

Where, ' $s_{X,0}$ ' is the number of vacuum events, ' $s_{X,1}$ ' the number of single-photon events, and ' ϕ_X ' is the phase error rate in the sifted 'X' basis. The parameter ' λ_{EC} ' provides a bound on the number of bits required for error correction. The security parameters ' ϵ_c ' and ' ϵ_s ' define the correctness and secrecy of the resulting key respectively [8, 9]. We refer the reader to Ref. [8] for a detailed analysis and explanation regarding Eq. (2).

² Polarization state of the photon.

4. *Security validation.* Once the secret key has been generated and shared between the parties, Alice and Bob can detect if an eavesdropper³ was present, by revealing a portion of the key [4]. In order to understand how an eavesdropper can be detected, consider a spy 'Eve', who is trying to steal the information that Alice sends to Bob (but without making her presence known), and thus measures Alice's photons as she sends them to Bob [10]. Eve will measure Alice's photon either in \mathcal{B}_+ or in \mathcal{B}_x basis, (just like Bob) and then sends each of the photons to Bob.

Figure 2: BB84 protocol scheme [11]. To summarize: $\lambda/2$ -polarising plates are placed at (a) and (b). Photons sent by Alice are randomly polarised (c), then Bob measures in either one of the bases (d), thus obtaining a string of bits (e). By comparing bases (f), Alice and Bob disregard uncorrelated bits, thus generating the secret key (g).

5. *Error correction & privacy amplification.* Because the quantum bit errors in the sifted key could either be a result of device imperfections or the presence of an eavesdropper, Alice and Bob must assume the worst case scenario in order to optimize security of the secret key (i.e. assuming that an eavesdropper was present). Using methods of classical information theory, a shorter but error-free key (for which Eve has no information of) can be generated [4].

Now, if Eve chooses the correct basis, then she can transmit the correct state to Bob, however, if she chooses the wrong basis she will measure (and transmit to Bob) the correct or wrong state with 50% probability each [12]. This of course means that with the presence of Eve, 25% of the photons Bob measures are wrong (not what Alice sent originally). Therefore, Alice and Bob can compare part of their key (by revealing a certain portion to one another) and if the quantum bit error rate⁴ (QBER) is $<25\%$, then it is unlikely that anyone intercepted the information along the way [5]. However, due to the probabilistic nature of the problem, error correction and privacy amplification procedures are still necessary to ensure the highest levels of security [4].

Finally, it can be noted that the bigger the portion of the key that they reveal to one another, the more certain they can be on whether an eavesdropper was present or not [10]. However, one must understand that the portion of the key that is revealed cannot then be used to send the encrypted

³ An unwanted third party trying to collect or modify the encrypted message

⁴ The ratio of the error rate to the attained key rate

message anymore, as it will be compromised over a classical link.

This property of the BB84 protocol makes it an extremely powerful encryption method, as one can detect if someone along the way is trying to access or alter the information.

In reality, two variants of the BB84 protocol exist: the standard protocol discussed above, in which the choice of basis occurs with equal probability [7, 8], and the efficient protocol, which allows for asymmetric basis choice with probabilities P_{B_+} and $1 - P_{B_+}$. While the standard BB84 uses both basis to generate the secret key and thus requires parameter estimation for both, efficient BB84 uses a single base to produce the secret key and the other basis for parameter estimation, resulting in higher secret key length (SKL) [8].

As mentioned earlier, one of the disadvantages of using the standard BB84 protocol in SatQKD is that more than 50% of the information is lost in the name of security, while more is lost due to other factors such as diffraction of light, the inverse square law, internal losses of the instrumentation and dark counts due to background radiation [12].

Moreover, it is worth noting that the single photon sources required by the protocol, able to send exactly 1 photon at a time with absolute certainty, do not exist [8]. Losses due to light propagation can be minimized using faint lasers such as Weak Coherent Pulse (WCP) sources, which are a practical way of generating a stream of randomly polarised single photon pulses [13].

Coherent states can be used to describe quantised light sources and are characterized by the coherent superposition of fock states⁵ [13]. Eq. (3) shows the general form of a coherent state.

$$|\alpha\rangle = e^{-\frac{1}{2}|\alpha|^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{\alpha^n}{\sqrt{n!}} |n\rangle \quad (3)$$

Where ' $|\alpha\rangle$ ' represents states of the quantised electromagnetic field that have a sensible classical limit (i.e. behave like a wave with $n \rightarrow \infty$, as described by Maxwell's equations), and ' $|\alpha|^2 = \mu$ ', the mean photon number in a given time interval [13].

Unfortunately, due to the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics, the number of photons in a WCP isn't always 1, meaning that sometimes the pulse can contain more than one photon, while other times it can contain zero photons (vacuum state) [12]. It is important to note that for security reasons, it is essential to avoid multi-photon pulses, as these can allow an eavesdropper to conduct a photon-number splitting attack [13, 14], thus compromising the safety of the quantum channel.

The probability of a WCP containing more than one photon is given by Eq. (4):

$$P(n > 1 | n > 0, \mu) = \frac{1 - P(0, \mu) - P(1, \mu)}{1 - P(0, \mu)} \approx \frac{\mu}{2} \quad (4)$$

Where the probability of finding ' n ' photons in a given coherent state with mean photon number ' μ ', follows the Poisson statistics [12], as: $P(n, \mu) = (\mu^n e^{-\mu}) / (n!)$.

As previously mentioned, it is important to keep the number of multi-photon pulses to a minimum [13], however this is not as simple as to minimize ' μ ', since this would increase the number of dark counts of the receiver [12, 14].

⁵ Quantum states of the electromagnetic field of mode ' \vec{k} ', with a well defined integer number of photons.

2. Satellites & Orbital Mechanics

To explore the realm of QKD for inter-satellite links, it is important to first explore the basics of orbital mechanics. The point of focus of this section will therefore be an explanation as to how satellites achieve orbit, and how they maintain it.

To understand how satellites are sent to orbit, one must be familiar with the concept of 'escape velocity', Eq. (5).

$$\vec{v}_e = \sqrt{\frac{2GM}{r}} \quad (5)$$

For a rocket to escape Earth's gravitational pull, it must achieve a radial speed (i.e. away from Earth's center of gravity) of $v_e = 11.186 \text{ km/s}$, (escape velocity of the Earth) [15]. Launching satellites into orbit creates many engineering challenges and ultimately limitations to the cargo weight and size. Weight limitations are due to the specific thrust to weight ratio requirement for the rocket to be able to achieve escape velocity. Because of these reasons and lower costs, it is important to look into the usage of smaller satellites such as cubesats.

Accurate calculations can be made using classical mechanics, that is Newton's law of gravitation and Kepler's third law. While Newton's law of gravitation doesn't explain more complicated effects that arise from objects with mass ' $M \gg M_{\oplus}$ ' (where M_{\oplus} is Earth's mass), it is a very good approximation as the local effects of general relativity for $M = M_{\oplus}$, are negligible [15]. Similarly, the satellites are assumed to be travelling at speeds $v \ll c$, meaning that effects arising from Special Relativity can be ignored. Finally, for the purpose of this project, it is safe to assume that the satellites experience minimal atmospheric drag when orbiting at heights above 400km ASL.

For circular orbits, the centripetal force ' \vec{F}_c ' matches the gravitational force ' \vec{F}_g ' and points towards the center of the orbit at all times (i.e. $\vec{F}_c = \vec{F}_g$).

Kepler's third law Eq. (6), relates the distance from the center of the orbit to the orbital period 'T' [15]. The orbital period of a satellite is then given by:

$$T = 2\pi\sqrt{\frac{r^3}{GM}} \quad (6)$$

In addition it is important to understand how satellites maintain their orbit around the Earth. Generally speaking, a satellite is said to be in a stable orbit around the Earth if its tangential velocity component is large enough such that the rate at which it 'falls' (accelerates) towards the Earth is equal to the rate at which Earth's surface 'curves away' from it (by the tangential velocity).

3. Light in vacuum & SatQKD links

Since the purpose of the report is to investigate how the optical link efficiency of a SatQKD network is affected by signal losses due to the diffraction of light, it is crucial to understand how light propagates through a vacuum.

Furthermore, to understand how light emitting diodes, avalanche photo-detectors and other types of transmitters and receivers work, one must be familiar with the quantum mechanical description of light; rather than considering light as a continuous propagating electromagnetic wave (described by Maxwell's equations), it is considered as individual quantum excitations of the harmonic oscillator associated with an electromagnetic field mode, that is photons [16].

This description allows for the invention of very accurate single photon detectors and sources, that are key to SatQKD based communications.

For a spherically symmetric light source, the light propagates radially outwards as the surface of a sphere (see Fig.3 below) with an ever increasing radius expanding at a rate of 'c', the speed of light. From conservation of energy, it follows that the intensity of light propagating in a vacuum is given by the 'Inverse Square Law':

$$\mathcal{I} = \frac{P}{4\pi r^2} \quad (7)$$

Where 'P' is the power of the source and 'r' the distance from the spherically symmetric source of illumination.

However, this is not the case for a beam of light originating from a laser. In this case, light propagation occurs in a well defined direction with minimal transverse propagation due to the spatial coherence of the light field [17]. From the inverse square law, it is clear that the further a detector is placed from the source, the more difficult it becomes for it to detect single photons. This is because the same amount of power is spread out onto a bigger surface area, resulting in lower intensity.

It is important to note that some sources of light are better than others. Generally speaking, for long range classical communications, lasers are preferred as the spread of the light over distance is much smaller than any other light source.

Figure 3: Representation of how light propagates in space, by the inverse square law [18].

Although the inverse square law implies that some information is inevitably lost over distance, this is not the only factor contributing to loss; another factor is due to the diffraction of light. Diffraction occurs whenever a propagating electromagnetic wave encounters and interacts with a physical obstacle, for example, whenever it passes through an aperture [19]. The aperture effectively becomes a secondary source of the propagating wave [20], resulting in a spread of the initial power over a larger surface area.

There are two ways of describing the diffraction of light and differentiating between the two is essential to obtain an accurate description of the phenomenon [19]; this is done via the Fresnel number:

$$F = \frac{R^2}{L \lambda} \quad (8)$$

Where 'R' is the radius of the aperture, 'L' the distance to the screen and 'λ' the wavelength. We distinguish between:

- Near field / Fresnel diffraction $\rightarrow F \sim 1$
- Far field / Fraunhofer diffraction $\rightarrow F \ll 1$

Figure 4: Representation of how light diffracts in space, given different Fresnel numbers ' N_F '. To the left: Fresnel diffraction and to the right: Fraunhofer diffraction [21].

Diffraction of light can be described to be in the near field if the distance to the screen is relatively small such that $L \cdot \lambda \approx R^2$. In the near field regime, the electric field takes up complex forms and can rarely be resolved analytically [20]. Far field diffraction occurs instead when $L \gg R^2/\lambda$. In this case, the electric field is described by the Fourier transform [19], which in cylindrical coordinates takes the form Eq. (9):

$$E(\rho, L) = \frac{k}{L} \int_0^\infty \rho' A(\rho') J_0\left(\frac{k \rho' \rho}{L}\right) d\rho' \quad (9)$$

Where " $k = 2\pi/\lambda$ " is the wavenumber, " $A(\rho')$ " the transmitter aperture electric field distribution, " ρ' " denotes the variable radius of the transmitter aperture, " ρ " the fixed radius of the receiver aperture and " J_0 " a Bessel function of the first kind.

The electric field and intensity relation is given by Eq. (10):

$$\mathcal{I} = \frac{1}{2} c \epsilon_0 E^2 \quad (10)$$

Because of the nature of the particle-wave duality of light, sometimes it is more convenient to use the quantum description of light rather than the classical one provided by Maxwell's equations [16]. In quantum mechanics, the general form of a quantised electric field is given by Eq. (11):

$$\hat{E}_{\vec{k}}(\chi) = \vec{\epsilon}_{\vec{k}} \sqrt{\frac{\hbar \omega_k}{2 \epsilon_0 V}} [\hat{a}_{\vec{k}} e^{-i\chi} + \hat{a}_{\vec{k}}^\dagger e^{i\chi}] \quad (11)$$

With: $\chi_{\vec{k}}(\vec{r}, t) = \omega_k t - \vec{k} \cdot \vec{r} - \pi/2$. Where ' $\vec{\epsilon}_{\vec{k}}$ ' is the polarisation vector, and the subscript ' \vec{k} ' denotes a specific mode of the EM-field with frequency ' ω_k ' contained within a volume 'V'.

Additionally, if we consider a quantised light field of frequency ω_L , then its Hamiltonian is given by Eq. (12):

$$\hat{H}_L = \hbar \omega_L (\hat{a}^\dagger \hat{a} + 1/2) \quad (12)$$

Where ' \hat{a} ' is the lowering operator and ' \hat{a}^\dagger ' the raising operator.

Equation (12) corresponds to the total energy of the light field generated by the photon [16].

Furthermore, contributing to the loss of information and overall a big limiting factor is the background radiation from the Sun, which makes it very difficult for satellites to communicate between one another while exposed to sunlight [5], as the number of extraneous counts⁶ and dark counts⁷ increases dramatically.

Because higher frequencies of light are desirable for SatQKD, it seems perfectly reasonable to consider UV light as a viable interval of wavelengths for use in quantum channel links.

However, this also depends upon the single photon sources and detectors operating at these wavelengths that are available and integratable onto satellites.

⁶ Clicks in the receiver device for photons originating from background radiation.

⁷ Clicks in the receiver device for vacuum state events (i.e. no incident photon).

II. Current State of the Field

Although the idea of satellite based QKD communication has been around for almost a century now, the field has been growing at a fast pace as new inter-satellite links in low-earth orbit (LEO) and geostationary orbit (GEO) have been established using phase coherent lasers for high sensitivity and power-efficient communications [22], thus providing proof of concept [5, 23]. Much of the technology required to build a global network between QKD communication satellites and optical ground stations (OGS) distributed across the planet (see Fig.5), is still in development phase.

The increased interest in quantum communication has accelerated the development and improvement of quantum technologies, with a focus on optimization [24]. Due to the exigent demand spanning across a multitude of quantum technologies, further development and optimization of various components is needed to meet the high standards required for their integration on smaller satellites such as CubeSats (weighing 1 Kg and with size in the order of 1 dm^3) [22]. Additionally, the need for efficient and secure QKD-link connections has made it desirable to have a network with a high degree of connectivity [25], thus requiring the optimization of the orbital topology for a network of satellites (see Fig.5).

Figure 5: A diagram showing a simple SatQKD network between two satellites and two ground stations.

While most transmitters and receivers installed and in use on satellites today utilize radio signals [26], it is essential to investigate the use of ultraviolet light for applications in QKD [27], as radio signals are unfit to satisfy the high rates of quantum key sharing and low losses required for relatively high bandwidths during daytime exposure. Because of the high amounts of background noise during daylight exposure, efficient QKD communication is currently unfeasible [28].

The current state of research in QKD space communication is seeing some important milestones being demonstrated (see Fig.6). In recent years, a lot of focus has gone into developing low Size, Weight and Power (SWaP) optical links [22] for use in small satellites like CubeSats, as these offer

excellent ground coverage when put in constellations and cluster orbits. These types of networks are very advantageous as the requirements for optical tracking systems (which usually come at a great cost of weight and size) are very low [22, 23], if not inexistent.

Because of their higher divergence of emissions, Optical Light Emitting Diode (LED) links have lower SWaP requirements compared to radio frequency based links [22], depending on satellite size and weight capacity, and are more suitable for implementation on small satellites as a result.

Gallium nitride (GaN) micro-LEDs have been shown to offer high bandwidths in the order of several Gbps [29] with a high degree of accuracy, making them excellent transmitters.

Under strict SWaP constraints of a CubeSat, a link composed of a single micro-LED transmitter and Single-Photon Avalanche Diode (SPADs) as receiver has been demonstrated to reach data rates up to 100 Mb/s with a sensitivity of 55.2 dBm over a range of 5.7 km [22]. Considering lower SWaP constraints (applicable to more small-sized-satellites) and micro-LED transmitter arrays, bandwidths could likely reach the required rates for applications in QKD.

The usage of light in the ultraviolet (UV) part of the electromagnetic spectrum has been proposed as a possible improvement in communication performance between satellites [27] (as it could allow for open QKD links during daylight hours). However, as far as I know, no complete study has been carried out to learn about the details of the advantages, disadvantages and possible problems of the development and implementation of new components onto satellites.

It seems clear that this is an important area of research which could lead to significant improvements in the performance of inter-satellite QKD communications.

Figure 6: QKD Milestones. A diagram showing the timeline of key milestones achieved in the field of QKD (adopted from [5]).

III. Methods

The main purpose of this report is to investigate the link efficiency of inter-satellite based quantum channels using wavelengths within the UV portion of the electromagnetic spectrum (10-400 nm).

The method used for investigating this query relies on the creation of a Python module able to provide accurate statistical simulations for the detection of single photons sent by a single photon source integrated onto one of two satellites orbiting the Earth.

The Python module is ultimately responsible for creating a .csv file containing data for the signal loss (and the respective timestamps) due to the diffraction of light for a single pass between the two satellites during which they have direct line of sight (DLOS) on one another. This file is then passed to the Satellite Quantum Modelling & Analysis (SatQuMA) software, which provides a numerical key rate analysis that determines the amount of expected secret key to be generated [30].

The key rate analysis provided by SatQuMA is based upon the two decoy state WCP BB84 protocol, for which one of three pulse intensities is randomly transmitted by Alice (rather than a single intensity) [30]; this method is implemented within the efficient BB84 protocol for improved security of the quantum link [8].

From the combination of the Python simulations module and SatQuMA, we can expect to develop understanding for the efficiency of QKD based communications between two satellites in a given specific orbital configuration.

The python module lays focus on two main aspects:

1. Simulation of the orbits of two satellites.
2. Simulation of single photon detection events during a pass.

The aim of the orbital simulations portion of the module is to provide an array containing the Relative Satellite Separation (RSS) (i.e. distance between the satellites) during the first pass (for which they have DLOS), with the corresponding time interval. This portion of the module allows us to customize parameters such as the altitude, relative starting point within the orbit, relative angle between the orbital planes and the number of orbital periods to take into consideration for the two satellites. Because all possible passes can be modeled by the first pass by changing the orbital parameters, for simplicity, only the first pass will be considered.

In addition to the file, the module outputs a 3D interactive plot of the orbital trajectories around the Earth, with no emphasis on position over ground, as well as two 2D plots, one showing the general trend in RSS with time (see Fig.7) and the other showing just the first pass, for which the two satellites have DLOS on one another. This is done to provide visual aid and help analyze various properties of the specific orbits and how they are related.

As mentioned in section I.B.3, it is important to make assumptions that can simplify the model, while keeping a high degree of accuracy. For simplicity, it is assumed that the satellites follow perfectly circular orbits, which enables the usage of Kepler's third law, and in addition any effects due to general relativity are neglected.

The second portion of the module aims at conducting single photon detection simulations for calculating the signal loss due to light diffraction as the satellites pass each other.

It is evident that the communications between the two satellites should be optimized for the closest approach in the time required to send the information, thus minimizing the loss of information due to diffraction and propagation of light via the inverse square law.

Figure 7: Left (a): 3D Plot of satellite orbital trajectories around the Earth. Blue and orange dots represent the starting positions of s1 and s2 respectively. The atmospheric layer ($H_0 = 100km$) is not shown in this plot. To the right (b): 2D plot showing the variation in RSS with Time. The blue portion of the plot marks the RSS for which the two satellites have DLOS (i.e. $RSS < L_{max}$) and can communicate.

The code for both portions of the Python simulations module highly relies on the usage of various packages including: NumPy, SciPy, csv, sys and finally matplotlib and plotly with the purpose of generating 2D and 3D plots respectively.

NumPy and SciPy have been very useful for storing data as well as computing calculations and operations involving large sets of data (arrays) in a relatively short time span. The 'sys' and 'csv' libraries have been used to format and store results into a '.csv' file.

Finally, because SatQuMA was originally designed to make SKL calculations for the quantum link between a single satellite and a ground station [30], some modifications have been made to the output data of the Python simulations module in order make it compatible with SatQuMA.

In addition to the time and loss, the output .csv file must also contain a column with data for an elevation angle. In the OGS to satellite link, this is the angle between the tangential line to the Earth at the OGS location, and the direct line of sight between the OGS and the satellite [8]. The reason this angle is important to consider, is that SatQuMA tries to find the optimum parameters and time window for which the SKL can be maximized [30].

Details regarding what this angle should be are discussed in the next section.

Please note that from now on, we will refer to the satellite in the lower orbit as 's1' and the one in the highest orbit as 's2'.

A. Satellites Orbital Simulations

Orbital simulations can be modelled with ease by making the relevant assumptions. For simplicity, it is assumed that the satellites follow perfectly circular orbits, which allows for the usage of Kepler's third law. While this may not be the case for all satellites, more often than not, communication satellites follow orbits that come very close to being circularly symmetric. In addition, because this project is not concerned or dealing with the precise timing of signals and time synchronization, any effects due to general (or special) relativity are neglected.

Spherical coordinates are used in order to calculate the exact position of each satellite (x, y, z) for every second that elapses. A time array is defined on the interval $[0, n \cdot T]$, where 'T' is defined to be the largest orbital period of the two satellites (thus, the highest satellite), while 'n' is an integer number specified by the user, namely the number of orbits that the module will consider for calculations.

$$\begin{aligned} x &= R \cos(\phi - \alpha) \sin(\theta - \beta) \\ y &= R \sin(\phi - \alpha) \sin(\theta - \beta) \\ z &= R \cos(\theta - \beta) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

With the polar angle given by: $\theta = \omega t$, where ' ω ' is the angular velocity of the satellite, $\phi = 2\pi$, while angles ' α ' and ' β ' are input parameters specified by the user. Note: we choose $\alpha = 0$ for satellite 1 and $\beta = 0$ for satellite 2 at all times.

Angle ' α ' is the relative angle between the two orbital planes (azimuthal angle). Angle ' β ' is the phase difference between satellite 1 relative to satellite 2; it affects the starting point of satellite 1 (see Fig. 7).

The inter-satellite separation (RSS) is given by:

$$RSS = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2 + (z_2 - z_1)^2} \quad (14)$$

While the maximum displacement between the two satellites before they lose direct line of sight of each other is:

$$L_{max} = \sqrt{R_1^2 - (R + H_0)^2} + \sqrt{R_2^2 - (R + H_0)^2} \quad (15)$$

Where R_1 and R_2 are the distances between the center of the orbit (Earth's geometrical center) and the respective satellite, while ' $R = 6371 \cdot 10^3$ ' is the radius of the Earth in meters, and ' $H_0 = 100 \cdot 10^3$ ' is the height of the most dense portion of the atmospheric layer in meters.

Note that for ' $R_{1,2} > R + H_0$ ', it is assumed that atmospheric drag is negligible (and no orbit can be achieved if this condition is not met). Additionally, it is important to understand that higher frequencies of light are likely absorbed by the atmosphere if propagating below H_0 .

This implies that for $RSS < L_{max}$, the satellites will have direct line of sight (DLOS) of one another and therefore, be able to communicate (see Fig.7). If this condition is not met, it assumed that the satellites do not have DLOS.

Finally, we define the elevation angle ' ξ ' between the two satellites as the angle between the direct line of sight between the two satellites and the local horizon line of the lower satellite (see Fig. 8).

Figure 8: Diagram showing the elevation angle ' ξ ' defined on the specific interval $\xi \in [-20.33^\circ, 90^\circ]$ for the case in which $R_1 < R_2$. Left (a): s2 is below the local horizon of s1 (blue line), thus the elevation angle is negative. Right (b): s2 appears above the local horizon of s1, so the elevation angle takes positive values.

The elevation angle can then be calculated by Eq. (16) for the case in which $R_1 < R_2$:

$$\sin(\xi) = \pm \left(\frac{R_1^2 + R_2^2 - L^2}{2LR_1} - \frac{R_1}{L} \right) \quad (16)$$

Where ' R_1 ' and ' R_2 ' are the distances from Earth's center to s1 and s2 respectively and ' L ' the RSS.

While in the case for which $R_1 > R_2$, the angle is given by Eq. (17):

$$\sin(\xi) = \pm \left(\frac{R_2^2 + R_1^2 - L^2}{2LR_2} - \frac{R_2}{L} \right) \quad (17)$$

The ' \pm ' symbol in front of Eq. (16) and Eq. (17) is a reminder that when the angle spans below the lower satellite's local horizon line, it must satisfy the condition: $\xi < 0$.

Given any two satellite orbital trajectories, the moment s2 becomes visible over the horizon from s1's perspective, the elevation angle is at a minimum ' ξ_{min} '; as the two satellites approach one another and pass each other, ξ increases from ξ_{min} up to ξ_{max} , at which point the elevation angle will start decreasing until it reaches ξ_{min} again.

B. Photon Detection Probability Simulations

This section will focus on the portion of the Python code that deals with the calculations of the photon detection probability, and thus, the loss.

First and foremost, it is important to emphasize that the only contribution to loss of information that will be simulated, is that due to diffraction of light. Therefore, signal loss due to background noise from Sunlight, false detections, pointing errors are all neglected.

In order to simulate photon detection probability and signal loss due to diffraction of light, the following assumptions are made:

- To simplify calculations, it is assumed that there is no background radiation from the Sun (no false detections). This is possible while the satellites are located in the Earth's shadow.
- No pointing errors: It is assumed that during the first pass, the relative orientation between the two satellites remains the same, such that integrated transmitters are perfectly aimed at the center the other satellites receiver aperture.
- It is assumed that all diffraction of light is due to the far field / Fraunhofer diffraction, with $F \ll 1$.
- Light propagates in a perfect vacuum.

We can model the signal loss due to diffraction of light given that it is mainly dependent upon five factors: the wavelength of light used, the intensity distribution at the transmitter, the diameters of the transmitter and receiver apertures, and naturally, the distance between them.

Given these parameters one can calculate what the intensity distribution of the photon is at the receiver aperture, by taking the Fourier transform Eq. (9) of the transmitter's intensity distribution function.

A derivation showing how the electric field of a photon changes due to far field diffraction as it propagates through a vacuum (described by Eq. (9)), can be obtained by considering geometrical implications for the propagation of light through a circular aperture. However, this derivation goes beyond the scope of this report and thus, will not be discussed any further.

The module accepts any transmitter intensity distribution that the user would like to use, as a function of the radial distance as defined in cylindrical coordinates.

Two additional parameters ' r_{Rx}^{min} ' and ' r_{Tx}^{min} ', allow the user to shape the transmitter and receiver apertures similarly to that of a 'Gregorian' or a 'Cassegrain' reflector telescope (i.e. an annulus or ring shape).

For a pre-defined resolution, the program will calculate for each point on the transmitter intensity distribution, the corresponding intensity at the receiver by the Fourier transform. With a high enough resolution (i.e. number of points), the intensity distribution at the receiver will take form as a continuous function (see Fig.9), thus allowing calculations for the photon detection probability. PDP calculations involve finding the amount of power as a portion of the total power, for which the intensity distribution overlaps onto the receiver aperture.

Note that the Fourier transform outputs the electric field, meaning that every point is then converted to the corresponding intensity value using Eq. (10).

Figure 9: Receiver intensity distribution. A plot showing the intensity distribution function at the receiver. This is known as an airy disk pattern (b). Peak intensity at $2 \cdot 10^{-20} \frac{W}{m^2}$ (a) for a flat top intensity distribution at transmitter of $127.3 \frac{W}{m^2}$.

Once the intensity distribution at the receiver is obtained, the program will commence the Photon Detection Probability calculations. The PDP for the given parameters, can be found by integrating the intensity distribution over the receiver aperture. In essence, this is the portion of a photon that will enter the receiver and be detected by it (see Fig. 10).

Figure 10: Receiver intensity distribution cross-section. Plot showing a 2D slice of the intensity distribution function at the receiver (a) and the receiver aperture bounds (marked in red) on the distribution (b). Distance from transmitting satellite is $L = 1000 \text{ km}$.

Finally, we define the total system loss as [8]:

$$\eta_{sys} = -10 \log_{10}(PDP \cdot \epsilon_{eo}) \tag{18}$$

Where ' ϵ_{eo} ' is the electro-optical efficiency corresponding to the internal loss caused by imperfections of the instrumentation used.

IV. Results & Analysis

In this section, we will have a close look at the data obtained from the simulations of three different orbital scenarios divided into anti-parallel, parallel and perpendicular cases for the orbital trajectories of the two satellites. It is worth noting that in each of the three cases, the closest approach between the two satellites is set at 190km of separation, that is the height difference between the orbits.

The following parameters will be used for all simulations:

H1	530 km	Pulse Repetition Rate	10^9 Hz
H2	720 km	Extraneous count probability	10^{-7}
λ	300 nm	ϵ_c	10^{-15}
d_T	0.1 m	ϵ_s	10^{-9}
d_R	0.3 m	Afterpulse probability	10^{-3}
Internal Loss	3 dB	QBERI	10^{-3}
Intensity Distribution of Tx (\mathcal{I}_{Tx})		127.3 W/m^2	

Table I: Relevant parameters used for the simulations. Python module (left), SatQuMA (right).

As the two satellites orbit at different altitudes, from Kepler's third law Eq. (6), it is clear that s2 takes more time to complete a full orbit as it travels slower than s1 and must cover more distance. In the given scenario, s1 orbits at an altitude of 530 km ASL, while s2 orbits at 720 km ASL, meaning that the maximum distance for which they can have direct line of sight corresponds to 5298 km (when taking into consideration a thick atmosphere that rises 100km ASL). This corresponds to a minimum elevation angle of $\xi_{min} = -20.33^\circ$.

An important question to answer before we start looking at the results, is how reasonable it is to assume that all diffraction of light is due to the far field / Fraunhofer diffraction, with $F \ll 1$. Figure 11 shows how the Fresnel number varies with RSS, and as we can see, the worst case scenario for which $RSS = 190 \text{ km}$, the Fresnel number is $F = 0.04386 \ll 1$.

Figure 11: Fresnel number against distance. Values calculated using Eq. (8), with a wavelength of $\lambda = 300 \text{ nm}$ and aperture radius of $r_{Tx} = 0.05 \text{ m}$.

A. Case 1: Anti-parallel orbits

The case for which two satellites orbit around the Earth on the same orbital plane and in opposite directions of one another (see Fig. 12), is without doubt the worst case scenario in terms of useful time available to send and receive information.

Figure 12: A diagram showing coplanar orbits for two satellites travelling in opposite directions.

The moment the elevation angle between s1 and s2 becomes greater or equal to the minimum elevation angle ξ_{min} , the satellites acquire a direct line of sight and can therefore start to exchange information. The relative distance between the two satellites (RSS) varies with time as shown in the following diagram (see Fig. 13).

Figure 13: Plots showing the variation of RSS with time. (Overall trend (a) & first pass (b)).

Note that the time axis for calculating the first pass, was shifted such that 't=0' corresponds to the time of closest approach (i.e. RSS = 190km).

It is expected that as the satellites get closer to one another, loss due to diffraction decreases until it reaches a minimum at the time of closest approach and then starts to rise again as they go past each other and RSS increases (see Fig. 14).

Figure 14: Plot showing the variation of loss with time for anti-parallel orbits. Minimum loss at the time of closest approach is 11 dB.

Additionally, from Fig. 14 we can see that the total system loss remains under $\eta_{sys} < 15 \text{ dB}$ for a time window of $\Delta t = 16 \text{ s}$ and a total of 32 seconds . This corresponds to a minimum PDP of about 3.2%. During the pass, the satellites spend around 1/5 of the time at a relative distance $RSS > 1000 \text{ km}$ for which the loss is above 25 dB, and the PDP is below 0.32%.

Figure 15: Variation of SKL with Time Window (Δt). Plot showing how the SKL changes with different time windows for anti-parallel orbits. In black the variation of SKL with Δt for standard parameters. Blue, orange and red curves have 1, 2 and 3 dB of additional loss to the system.

From SKL calculations for this specific pass, we can model how the SKL varies with a particular time window ' Δt ' ranging from $-\Delta t$ to $+\Delta t$ around $t = 0$ (see Fig. 15). Here we can see how the SKL curve varies with additional system loss: the greater the system loss, the lower the possible SKL to be generated, as expected.

Moreover, it is interesting to see that the greater the additional system loss, the smaller the effect it has on the SKL generated. This can be seen by comparing the difference in SKL between the black and blue curves and that between the orange and red curves; although the (added) system loss difference is the same in both cases (1 dB), it is clear that the latter results in a smaller difference in generated SKL (more details on this later).

Because at longer distances the QBER is higher [5], there is an optimum time window for which the satellites are able to exchange a relatively high amount of secret key. Taking into consideration bigger time windows beyond that point provides minimal improvements on the SKL to be generated [8].

From Fig. 15 it is clear that by simply considering a bigger time interval for which the satellites have DLOS on one another does not lead to significant improvements in the SKL yield. After a time window (Δt) of about 100 seconds, improvements in key generation are very small, and become smaller with higher time window intervals.

B. Case 2: Parallel orbits

Similarly to case 1, the two satellites orbit around the Earth on the same orbital plane but in the same direction as shown in Fig. 16. This is by far the best case scenario in terms of useful time available to send information to one another.

Figure 16: A diagram showing coplanar orbits for two satellites travelling in the same direction. In the green orbit s1 will eventually overtake s2 (in the orange orbit) as it travels faster.

When compared to case 1, aside from the much bigger time window of 35,307 seconds, for which the satellites have DLOS on one another, in this scenario, the RSS is minimized for a much longer period of time.

Figure 17: Plots showing the variation of RSS with time. (Overall trend (a) & first pass (b)).

The time interval for which the satellites pass each other is 49.2 times longer than that of the anti-parallel orbits case. Additionally, from Fig. 18 we can see that the total system loss remains at a minimum range of values $\eta_{sys} < 15 \text{ dB}$ for a much longer period of time corresponding to a time window of $\Delta t = 800 \text{ s}$.

Figure 18: Plot showing the variation of system loss with time for parallel orbits. Minimum loss at the time of closest approach is 11 dB.

To get an idea of how much the loss affects the PDP, we find that PDP reaches a value of 1% when the satellites are separated by a distance of 553 km at $t = -1690$ s.

Figure 19: Variation of SKL with Time Window (Δt). Plot showing how the SKL changes with different time windows for parallel orbits. In black the variation of SKL with Δt for standard parameters. Blue, orange and red curves have 1, 2 and 3 dB of additional loss to the system.

Although taking into consideration bigger time windows can lead to significant improvements in SKL over the same time intervals considered for anti-parallel orbits (and as we will see, for perpendicular orbits), if we were to take into consideration large enough time windows, we would see the same as for Fig. 15, for which after a certain range of time windows, improvements in SKL become insignificant (see appendix for more detail).

C. Case 3: Perpendicular orbits

Unlike case 1 and 2, the two satellites orbit around the Earth on perpendicular orbital planes, meaning that the direction in which they travel is irrelevant (see Fig.20). In this case, we expect the two satellites to be able to see each other for a longer period of time than in case 1, but a much smaller period of time than in case 2.

Figure 20: A diagram showing two satellites in perpendicular orbits.

However, it is worth noting that as they approach each other, due to the high relative velocity, the assumption that they can maintain a continuous orientation match may not be satisfied in a real life scenario.

Figure 21: Plots showing the variation of RSS with time for perpendicular orbits. (Overall trend (a) & first pass (b)).

From Fig. 22 we can see that the total system loss remains at a minimum range of values $\eta_{sys} < 15\text{ dB}$ corresponding to a time window of $\Delta t = 23\text{ s}$. This is a slightly longer period of time than for anti-parallel orbits but still much shorter than for parallel orbits (35 times smaller).

Figure 22: Plot showing the variation of PDP with time for perpendicular orbits. Minimum loss at the time of closest approach is 11 dB.

Once again we plot the generated SKL with the time window in Fig. 15:

Figure 23: Variation of SKL with Time Window (Δt). Plot showing how the SKL changes with different time windows for perpendicular orbits. In black the variation of SKL with Δt for standard parameters. Blue, orange and red curves have 1, 2 and 3 dB of additional loss to the system.

Comparably to case 1, the SKL reaches a maximum for a time window around 100 *seconds*, after which point SKL rises very slowly with the time window.

D. Important relations

Perhaps the most important relation from our model is that between the loss and the RSS during the first pass, as shown in Fig. 24.

As expected, the greater the RSS, the higher the loss due to diffraction. However, as the satellites pass each other, because RSS increases at slower rates until reaching a maximum (see Fig.21), the PDP also decreases at a higher rates over shorter distances between the satellites and likewise we can see that loss also increases at higher rates on the left side of Fig. 24 than the right hand side. The plot shows a maximum system loss of 39.6 dB corresponding to a PDP of 0.01% . The detection probability increases to a maximum of 7.87% at the time of closest approach at $t = 0$, at a minimum distance of 190 km and minimum system loss of 11 dB .

Figure 24: Plot showing the variation of system loss with RSS during the first pass.

It is worth noting that because all of the system parameters are kept constant (i.e. wavelength, transmitter and receiver apertures, intensity distribution at transmitter and heights of the orbits), the relation showed in Fig. 24 holds for all of the three cases presented above, as loss becomes only a function of RSS.

With the data obtained for the three separate cases, we can now compare each of them directly to get an idea of which of the relative orbital geometries can provide optimal SKL generation rates during a single pass. From Fig. 25, it is not surprising to see that the case for which the orbits are perpendicular (blue curve) yields a higher SKL than the case for which the orbits are anti-parallel. The reason for this, is that the satellites in anti-parallel orbits spend much less time 'close' to one another, meaning that signal loss is overall much higher within an arbitrary time window Δt . As expected, the case for which the orbits are parallel provides by far the longest SKL.

While a maximum SKL of $9.24 \cdot 10^8$ bits can be achieved in the anti-parallel case for a maximum time window of $\Delta t = 351$ seconds, given the same time window, a maximum SKL of $1.30 \cdot 10^9$ is achieved for the perpendicular orbits and a significantly higher SKL of $1.55 \cdot 10^{10}$ bits is achieved in the parallel case. For the parallel case, this corresponds to a 41% improvement over the perpendicular orbits and a 1,578% improvement over the anti-parallel orbits.

Figure 25: SKL generation comparison by case. The plot compares the variation in SKL with different time windows for the first pass of each case as described above. Note: the secondary y-axis (right) corresponds to the SKL of the grey curve.

This is to show just how much better longer single passes are at generating secret key than shorter and faster ones. Note how the SKL generation rates for parallel orbits seems to grow at a much faster pace throughout the same time windows than those of the anti-parallel and perpendicular cases. This is mainly due to the fact that in the parallel case, the satellites are overall much closer to one another than in the other 2 cases during this time interval.

Furthermore, it is interesting to investigate how the SKL changes as a function of the angle between the orbits (orbital angle) ' α ' (see Fig. 26).

Figure 26: SKL generation against orbital angle. The plot compares the variation in SKL with different orbital angles (α) for the first pass. The satellites travel in opposite directions and the point of closest approach in each case occurs at $RSS_{min} = 190 \text{ km}$. The SKL is calculated for a time window of $\Delta t = 100 \text{ s}$ (blue), $\Delta t = 200 \text{ s}$ (orange) and $\Delta t = 290 \text{ s}$ (green).

It is important to note that this relation was obtained for the case in which the two satellites travel in opposite directions. It is needless to say that if we were to consider the case for which the satellites travel in the same direction, the SKL generated would decrease with increasing angle α between the orbital planes as on average, the satellite spend less time 'close' to each other (thus minimizing loss).

From Fig. 26 it is clear that increasing the orbital angle α leads to a higher SKL yield. This is expected and consistent with the data reported in Fig. 25, since at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ the satellites have anti-parallel orbits and with increasing angle the time window for which the RSS is minimized, also increases, leading to smaller loss and higher SKL. Additionally, we can see how increasing the time window only leads to discrete SKL generation rate improvements up to a certain point (in this case from $\Delta t = 100s$ to $\Delta t = 200s$), after which the improvements become minimal.

Finally, after our observations of how the difference in SKL was affected by loss to different extents depending on the levels of additional loss, it seems natural to have a closer look at how the SKL varies with additional system loss, given a specific time window (see Fig. 27).

Figure 27: SKL against added Loss. The plot compares the variation in SKL with additional loss during the first pass for the anti-parallel case. The time window taken in consideration is $\Delta t = 150s$. The relation matches that of an exponential decay with equation:

$$SKL \approx 9.0732 \cdot 10^8 \cdot e^{-0.242} \text{ bits.}$$

In the above plot, it is clear that the achievable SKL decreases with additional system losses as expected; however, we can also notice how the extent to which the additional system loss lowers the SKL generation rates decreases with increasing values of system loss. For example, the difference in SKL between 0 dB and 1 dB is $\Delta SKL = 1.88 \cdot 10^8$ bits, while for the same increase in system loss between 10 dB and 11 dB , the difference in SKL becomes $\Delta SKL = 1.77 \cdot 10^7$ bits.

V. Discussion & Conclusion

We have discussed the possibility for future work to provide better insight into the usage of UV light in SatQKD links, as well as the benefits that this could lead to.

Furthermore, by taking into account different scenarios, we have seen how the attainable SKL varies with the time window centered around the time of closest approach as well as how it varies with additional system losses.

The simulations conducted for a wavelength of 300 nm (see list of parameters in Tab. I in the appendix) and a time window of $\Delta t = 351\text{ seconds}$ showed an attainable SKL of $9.24 \cdot 10^8$ bits for anti-parallel orbits, $1.30 \cdot 10^9$ bits for perpendicular orbits and $1.55 \cdot 10^{10}$ bits for parallel orbits. While for anti-parallel and perpendicular orbits the SKL generated differed by a few 100 million bits, the case for which the orbits are parallel outmatched the anti-parallel case by $1.46 \cdot 10^{10}$ bits and the perpendicular case by $1.42 \cdot 10^{10}$ (note that this difference rises to hundreds of billions of bits for larger time windows).

Within a SatQKD communications network, it may not be possible for constellations of satellites to be in parallel orbits, and from our results, we can deduce that in order to achieve a comparably high SKL yield, the SKL could be generated over multiple passes between satellites that are in perpendicular orbits [5, 8].

Additionally, simulations were carried out in order to find how the attainable SKL varies with the orbital plane angle α for the case of anti-parallel orbits. Starting from the anti-parallel case, increments in the angle result in higher SKL yields as expected, since the time for which the two satellites are closest increases such that system losses are minimized. Moreover it can be noted from Fig. 26, that the rate at which the SKL increases for increments in α , rises with bigger angles; meaning that a 15° increase from 0° will result in a smaller increment in SKL than a 15° increase from 60° .

Finally, we have seen how the attainable SKL varies with additional system loss for a specific time window. From Fig. 27 we can see that reductions in SKL (ΔSKL) decrease with increasing system loss. This is likely due to the dependency of the phase error rate for single photon events on the number of single photon events and bit errors associated to each event [9].

It is worth mentioning that as the satellites approach each other in the case of parallel orbits, because they travel in the same direction, the elevation angle between the two changes over longer periods of time, meaning that low pointing errors and accurate orientation matching would likely be possible. The same, however, can not be said in the case of anti-parallel or perpendicular orbits, as this would pose much more of a challenge due to the high relative velocity between the satellites as they pass each other. Moreover, SWaP requirements would set constraints which would greatly limit the quality of the tracking systems that can be used.

For this reason, further development of the python module to include point tracking simulations, would lead to more accurate results and lower estimates for the attainable SKL mainly over case 1 and 3. Further improvements to the accuracy of the simulations conducted in this report could also follow from additional development of SatQuMA to simulate extraneous counts due to a varying source of background radiation based upon position and orientation.

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A. Appendix

A table of constants used for the simulations.

Gravitational constant	$G = 6.6743 \cdot 10^{-11} \frac{Nm^2}{kg^2}$
Mass of the Earth	$M_{\oplus} = 5.972 \cdot 10^{24} kg$
Radius of the Earth	$R = 6371 \cdot 10^3 m$
Speed of Light	$c = 299,792,458 \frac{m}{s}$

Table II: Important constants

The table below shows all the possible input parameters that can be specified in the python simulations module.

H_1	Height ASL of Satellite 1 (Km)
H_2	Height ASL of Satellite 2 (Km)
α	Relative angle between orbital planes (rad)
β	Phase difference of Satellite 1 relative to Satellite 2 (% of 2π)
n	Number of orbits to consider in calculations
d_T	Transmitter's aperture diameter (m)
d_R	Receiver's aperture diameter (m)
r_{Tx}^{min}	Inner radius of transmitter's aperture (m)
r_{Rx}^{min}	Inner radius of receiver's aperture (m)
λ	Wavelength (nm)
$I_{Tx}(r)$	Transmitter intensity distribution function (as a function of 'r')
Internal Loss	Loss due to instrumentation inefficiencies
K	Time step for detection probability calculations (s)

Table III: List of input parameters for the Python simulations module.

As discussed in section IV.2, we can clearly see that from a bigger sample of data the relationship between the SKL and the time window takes the same form as that of the anti-parallel and perpendicular cases, just spanned over a much larger time window.

Figure 28: Variation of SKL with Time Window (Δt). Plot showing how the SKL changes with different time windows for the first pass for the case in which satellites travel in parallel orbits.